

REVIEW ARTICLE

Human talent and transdisciplinarity from a bibliographic review

Talento humano y transdisciplinarietà a partir de una revisión bibliográfica

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Abstract The study analyzed the application of transdisciplinarity in human talent management to identify its benefits, challenges, and opportunities. A systematic literature review was conducted using the PRISMA protocol based on studies published between 2002 and 2022 in high-impact scientific databases. The findings showed that transdisciplinarity facilitates the integration of knowledge from multiple disciplines, which drives organizational innovation, strategic competencies, and informed decision-making. Relevant obstacles were also identified, such as resistance to change, limited training in transdisciplinary methodologies, and difficulty consolidating multidisciplinary teams. It was concluded that implementing transdisciplinary approaches strengthens organizations' sustainability and adaptability, provided collaborative training strategies and management models are applied. It is recommended that transdisciplinary training programs be incorporated at the university level and in continuing education to improve organizational performance and competitiveness in complex contexts.

Keywords transdisciplinarity, human talent management, organizational innovation, strategic competencies, organizational sustainability.

Resumen El estudio analizó la aplicación de la transdisciplinarietà en la gestión del talento humano con el propósito de identificar sus beneficios, desafíos y oportunidades. Se realizó una revisión bibliográfica sistemática bajo el protocolo PRISMA, a partir de estudios publicados entre 2002 y 2022 en bases de datos científicas de alto impacto. Los hallazgos evidenciaron que la transdisciplinarietà facilita la integración de conocimientos provenientes de múltiples disciplinas, lo que impulsa la innovación organizacional, el desarrollo de competencias estratégicas y la toma de decisiones informadas. Asimismo, se identificaron obstáculos relevantes como la resistencia al cambio, la escasa formación en metodologías transdisciplinarias y la dificultad para consolidar equipos multidisciplinarios. Se concluyó que la implementación de enfoques transdisciplinarios fortalece la sostenibilidad y adaptabilidad de las organizaciones, siempre que se apliquen estrategias de formación y modelos de gestión colaborativos. Se recomienda incorporar programas de capacitación en transdisciplinarietà tanto en el ámbito universitario como en la formación continua para mejorar el desempeño organizacional y la competitividad en contextos complejos.

Palabras clave transdisciplinarietà, gestión del talento humano, innovación organizacional, competencias estratégicas, sostenibilidad organizacional.

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Introduction

Human talent management faces unprecedented challenges in digital transformation, globalization, and technological advances. Organizations require innovative approaches to adapt to changing scenarios, foster creativity, and ensure sustainable development. Transdisciplinarity has emerged as a key alternative for integrating knowledge from various disciplines and generating effective solutions in organizational management (Mancebo, 2024).

This article analyzes the application of transdisciplinarity in human talent management, identifying its benefits, challenges, and opportunities. A systematic bibliographic review, based on the PRISMA protocol, seeks to provide an updated understanding of the state of the art in this field and offer recommendations for implementing transdisciplinary approaches in different organizational contexts.

According to Callaos (2024), transdisciplinarity facilitates the integration of knowledge at the organizational level and strengthens communication between multidisciplinary teams, promoting greater collaboration and efficiency in decision-making. In human talent management, this approach allows for the design of adaptive strategies, fostering innovation, and improving the training of professionals to face the challenges of the digital economy (Díaz, 2024).

Recent research has shown that transdisciplinarity significantly impacts building strategic competencies such as complex problem-solving, cognitive flexibility, and data-driven decision-making. Ramírez et al. (2024) highlight that integrating transdisciplinary approaches into human talent management is critical for developing adaptive leadership and generating innovative solutions in uncertain environments.

Furthermore, the increasing automation and digitalization of work have driven the need to rethink how organizations manage their human capital. Knowledge management, continuing education, and interpersonal skills training have become fundamental pillars for business sustainability (Flórez-Espinal, 2024). In this sense, transdisciplinarity favors the integration of knowledge into work environments and enables the development of soft skills that complement workers' technical capabilities.

The concept of transdisciplinarity in human talent management has evolved toward a more holistic approach, where integrating different disciplines allows for addressing organizational problems from a broader perspective. Recent research has shown that transdisciplinarity contributes significantly to improving innovation in human resource management and developing continuous learning approaches that strengthen workers' adaptability (Díaz, 2024).

For example, incorporating transdisciplinary strategies has enabled the development of knowledge management programs that improve collaboration and communication among

multidisciplinary teams. By integrating disciplines such as sociology, organizational psychology, and artificial intelligence, these programs have proven effective in improving organizational efficiency and data-driven decision-making (Ramírez et al., 2024).

Likewise, applying trans-complex principles in public management has improved organizations' responsiveness to environmental changes. Mancebo (2024) points out that incorporating trans-complex approaches in human talent management facilitates the identification of emerging trends and enables the design of proactive strategies that guarantee organizational sustainability.

Implementing transdisciplinary approaches in human talent management offers numerous benefits, among which the integration of various disciplines allows for generating creative ideas and the development of disruptive solutions in human talent management (Callaos, 2022).

Transdisciplinarity encourages continuous learning and acquiring skills such as critical thinking, problem-solving, and evidence-based decision-making (Flórez-Espinal, 2024). Combining methodologies and tools from different fields of knowledge allows for optimizing human resource management and improving organizational efficiency (Díaz, 2024).

The application of transdisciplinary strategies represents a paradigmatic evolution in human talent management. It enables creating equitable, inclusive, and sustainable work environments by converging knowledge from disciplines such as organizational sociology, work psychology, artificial intelligence, and applied ethics.

As Ramírez et al. (2024) propose, the configuration of transdisciplinary collaborative ecosystems has expanded the frameworks of inclusion and participation within Latin American organizations and transformed leadership dynamics toward more participatory and distributed models. This perspective is consistent with Chiavenato's vision (2009), which argues that modern talent management should focus on the comprehensive development of people as strategic agents of organizational change.

For his part, Flórez-Espinal (2024) highlights that the acquisition of soft skills from a transdisciplinary matrix, particularly those linked to emotional intelligence, organizational empathy, and intercultural communication, is seen as a necessary response to the complexity of today's work environments. This line of argument aligns with Drucker's thinking (1999), who anticipated that knowledge and human capital management would constitute the main competitive differentiators in the 21st-century economy.

Similarly, Ulrich (2016) emphasizes the importance of human resources professionals acting as cultural architects, facilitating organizational environments that value diversity,

continuous learning, and adaptability. In this sense, transdisciplinarity enables an integrative approach to address organizational complexity and redefines human talent's role as the linchpin of innovation, sustainability, and structural transformation in contemporary organizations.

However, as Ramírez et al. (2024) point out, the adoption of transdisciplinarity in human talent management also presents specific challenges:

Resistance to change: Many organizations still operate under rigid hierarchical structures that make it challenging to implement transdisciplinary approaches (Mancebo, 2024).

Lack of training in transdisciplinary methodologies: There is a gap in higher education and vocational training programs regarding teaching transdisciplinary methodologies applied to human talent management (Díaz, 2024).

Difficulty integrating multidisciplinary teams: Collaboration between professionals from different disciplines requires developing practical communication skills and implementing leadership strategies that foster cooperation (Callaos, 2022).

Since this study's methodology follows a rigorous approach to selecting scientific literature, the findings will provide insight into how transdisciplinarity can optimize human talent management and strengthen organizations' adaptability in the digital age.

The analysis of transdisciplinarity in human talent management represents a key contribution to developing more efficient, sustainable, and innovative management models. Adopting transdisciplinary approaches allows for generating strategic solutions that optimize training, leadership, and decision-making in dynamic organizational environments. However, for effective implementation, it is essential to overcome cultural and organizational barriers and promote training in transdisciplinary methodologies in higher education and job training programs.

Methodology

This study was carried out through a systematic bibliographic review to analyze the application of transdisciplinarity in human talent management. The PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) was used to ensure rigor, transparency, and comprehensiveness in collecting and analyzing relevant scientific literature.

The information search was conducted in high-impact databases such as Scopus and Web of Science, selected for their broad coverage of the social sciences and business management. The search period included studies published between 2002 and 2022 to cover the conceptual and methodological evolution of the transdisciplinary approach to human talent management.

To identify relevant studies, Boolean operators were used, combining the following keywords: "transdisciplinarity" AND "human talent management" and "organizational innovation" OR "competency development". Additionally, sources obtained through cross-referencing and bibliographies of relevant articles were included.

The inclusion criteria were established: articles published in peer-reviewed scientific journals between 2002 and 2022; studies in Spanish or English; and research addressing transdisciplinarity in the context of human talent management and its impact on organizational innovation and competency development.

In addition, exclusion criteria are studies lacking empirical evidence or focusing exclusively on disciplinary approaches without considering transdisciplinary integration, documents that are not peer-reviewed, or studies that show obvious methodological biases.

The selection of studies was carried out in three phases: Identification: 150 potentially relevant studies were initially retrieved from the search strategy. Screening: Titles and abstracts were reviewed, and 90 studies that did not meet the inclusion criteria were excluded. Eligibility: The full texts of 60 studies were assessed, of which 30 were selected for final inclusion in the review.

Mendeley software was used to manage and organize bibliographic references, ensuring adequate systematization of the information.

The study employed a thematic analysis methodology to systematically examine the selected literature, identifying recurrent patterns and trends across the sources. The findings were organized into three key thematic categories: (1) transdisciplinary approaches applied to human talent management, (2) observed impacts on organizational performance and innovation, and (3) recommendations and implementation models proposed by the authors. This structured approach allowed for a comprehensive synthesis of the research, highlighting both theoretical frameworks and practical insights in the field.

Applying this method allowed for a deep and structured understanding of the influence of transdisciplinarity on human talent management, providing a solid foundation for developing well-founded conclusions and recommendations.

Results and discussion

The literature review on the application of transdisciplinarity in human talent management reveals significant findings that underscore its relevance and the associated challenges in today's organizational context.

Transdisciplinarity allows for integrating diverse disciplines, overcoming the limitations of single-disciplinary approaches. Serquera (2025) points out that this approach

seeks to go beyond interdisciplinarity, promoting an integration that transcends disciplinary boundaries. This integration facilitates a more holistic understanding of organizational problems, enabling more innovative and effective solutions.

Figure 1 presents a diagram of how transdisciplinarity impacts human talent management, integrating different areas of knowledge to improve organizational innovation.

Figure 1. Transdisciplinary integration in human talent management.

As seen in Figure 1, integrating different disciplines favors strategic decision-making by combining approaches from psychology, management, and data analysis. This approach is consistent with the proposal by Ramírez et al. (2024), who argue that transdisciplinarity enables better organizational problem-solving.

Organizations that adopt transdisciplinary approaches demonstrate a greater capacity to adapt to changing environments. Cepeda (2023) highlights that emerging organizations open to transdisciplinarity can interpret the changing environment, allowing greater structural and deliberative flexibility.

Transdisciplinarity fosters the development of advanced cognitive skills and creativity within organizations. Flórez-Espinal (2024) argues that this approach fosters innovation by integrating multiple perspectives and knowledge. Furthermore, transdisciplinary training broadens professionals' skill sets, improving their ability to adapt to dynamic work environments.

Despite its benefits, implementing transdisciplinary approaches faces significant challenges. Pirela and Alvarado (2024) point out that traditional management structures, characterized by autocratic and rigid processes, can hinder transdisciplinary knowledge integration. Promoting an organizational culture that values flexibility and knowledge sharing is essential to overcome these barriers.

Organizational culture plays a crucial role in the adoption of transdisciplinary approaches. A study published in *SciELO* (Rodríguez, 2008) analyzes forms of organizational behavior and their cultural models, emphasizing the introduction of new management tools and dimensions that facilitate transdisciplinarity. Fostering a culture that values collaboration and the integration of diverse disciplines is fundamental to the success of this approach.

Transdisciplinarity in human talent management offers an integrative framework that enables organizations to address the complexity and dynamism of today's environment. This approach facilitates innovation, adaptability, and sustainable organizational development by promoting the integration of multiple disciplines and perspectives. However, its implementation requires a cultural and structural transformation that supports flexibility, collaboration, and continuous learning.

Conclusions

Transdisciplinarity in human talent management has emerged as a critical strategy for organizations navigating today's complex and rapidly evolving business landscape. By integrating diverse disciplines and perspectives, companies gain a more comprehensive understanding of organizational challenges, enabling innovative and effective solutions. This approach not only enriches knowledge but also enhances adaptability—a crucial capability in dynamic markets. However, implementing transdisciplinarity presents significant challenges, particularly in traditional management structures that often prioritize rigid, siloed thinking over collaborative approaches. To succeed, organizations must cultivate a culture that embraces cross-disciplinary collaboration, flexibility, and continuous knowledge sharing, requiring both structural and cultural transformation. Equally important is developing transdisciplinary competencies among employees, ensuring they can thrive in fluid work environments while driving creativity and innovation. Ultimately, transdisciplinarity provides a key competitive advantage, empowering organizations to break down traditional barriers, foster collaborative learning, and position themselves for sustained success in an interconnected, ever-changing global economy.

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Conflicts of interest

The author declares that have no conflicts of interest.

Author contributions

Renier Esquivel: Conceptualization, data curation, formal

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